

ROMANTICISM IN “PRIDE AND PREJUDICE”

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Annotation.

The following article reveals some elements of Romanticism in Jane Austin's novel "Pride and Prejudice".

Key words.

Romanticism, respect for nature, idealization of woman, pride, love.

Аннотация.

В данной статье раскрываются некоторые элементы романтизма в романе Джейн Остин «Гордость и предубеждение».

Ключевые слова.

романтизм, уважение природы, идеализация женщины, гордость, любовь.

Annotatsiya.

Quyidagi maqola Jejn Ostinning "G'urur va Andisha" romanidagi romantizmning ba'zi elementlarini ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar.

Romantizm, tabiatni hurmat qilish, ayolni ideallashtirish, g'urur, sevgi.

Romanticism is a literary movement that dates back in the late 18th century until the end of the 19th century, however its impact can be observed in modern literature. The characteristic features of the movement marked by a focus on the individual's freedom, respect for nature, and idealization of women.

The term *Romanticism* does not illustrate the concept of love, despite the fact, it is taken from the French word "*romant*" meaning romance. So, Romanticism, mainly concerns about feelings and thoughts of the writer.

Thus, the following primary characteristics of Romanticism is to be marked in the novel: respect for nature, focus on the individual, observance of isolation, idealization of women and personification.

There are many romantic writers such as William Wordsworth, John Keats, Percy Bysshe Shelley, Mary Shelley who contributed their works and attracted numerous readers.

Writing through a time when the common standard was moving from perfection of the Enlightenment to those of Romanticism, Jane Austen's creative writing is often considered as manifesting aspects of both movements. There is no doubt that a reader can easily identify some elements of Romanticism in Jane Austen's famous novel "Pride and Prejudice".

The author emphasizes a characteristic feature of the Romanticism at the first lines of "Pride and Prejudice": "It is a universally acknowledged truth that a single man in control of a good chance must be in want of a wife⁹⁵" which not only attracts a reader with romantic phrase but also confirms one of the features of the Romanticism. Similarly, a woman in Austen's period should be successfully married as it would guarantee bright future. And the author explains it in optimistic way that a man should love and support a woman as soon as he is financially and morally ready for marriage.

There is another Romanticism feature that can be observed in the passage.

"Adieu to disappointment and spleen. What are men to rocks and mountains?"⁹⁶

Jane Austen quotes heroines' love for nature in few lines over her fall upon the Lake District with her own aunt and uncle. She emotionally overweighs naturalistic love to human love.

Continuously, the depiction of nature is widely illustrated around Elizabeth; the picture is used not only to differentiate her visually but it has some symbolical features as well. Firstly, Elizabeth's clothes in the majority of the scenes matches with nature to some extent, whether in its floral patterns or in the mile natural tones, they are usually brown, green or ivory. Secondly, while walking into Meryton with her own sisters Kitty and Lydia, they were in a ruby red, whereas Elizabeth was wearing again a green coat and a plain brown bonnet that are very natural to her. Moreover, the Bennet family's appearance at the Netherfield ball is the best illustration of this color combination; when Elizabeth was wearing a green coat with natural flowers in her hair differs from Mrs. Bennet and Jane's wearing bright pink clothes.

⁹⁵ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

⁹⁶ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003

Austin could professionally reveal her bored manner from urban affairs which attributes to Romanticism by Sir William Lucas character. Here he prefers moving from town life which later gives him pleasure to live in countryside: "Sir William Lucas had been previously in trade in Meryton, where he had made an enduring fortune, and risen to the honor of knighthood by an address to the king during his mayoralty."⁹⁷ The passage shows how a rich honored person changed his lifestyle. For Sir Lucas his status and job security do not make sense and he prefers to live close to nature.

"The difference had perhaps been felt too strongly. It had given him a distaste to his business, and to his residence in a small market town; and, in leaving them both, he had unfastened with his family to a house about a mile from Meryton, denominated from that period Lucas Lodge, where he could think with pleasure of his own significance and released by business, occupy himself solely in being secular to all the world."⁹⁸. The given passage notes that a rich person like Mr. Lucas could easily change his lifestyle no matter he earned a great fortune for the sake of love for nature; and this is another justification of Romanticism.

Reading the novel, one witnesses numerous depictions of beautiful nature. In the scene of Netherfield where Elizabeth, walking through the garden, came across a dog and started childishly to play with it on the grass. It undoubtedly means that Elizabeth as a part of nature stands in a line with a creation of nature – dog, playing and running side by side. She can not be as happy anywhere else as welcoming Pemberley. As Pemberley's beautiful natural setting is portrayed in the book – "Elizabeth had never seen a scene for which nature had done more, or where natural charm had been so little counteracted by an awkward taste. ...and at that moment she felt, that to be girlfriend of Pemberley might be something!"⁹⁹

Austin represents a beautiful girl as an angel through Bingley's opinion about Miss Bennet: "Bingley had never met with more pleasing people or prettier girls in his life; ...as to Miss Bennet, he could not draw up an angel more beautiful."¹⁰⁰ He sometimes calls them as sweet: "Mrs. Hurst and her sister allowed it to be so - but still they admired her and liked her, and said her to be a sweet girl,..."¹⁰¹

The most striking and notable feature of romanticism which is highlighted in the novel is a proposal of Darcy. The author describes the sentimentalistic

⁹⁷ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

⁹⁸ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

⁹⁹ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

¹⁰⁰ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

¹⁰¹ Austen Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. - New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

atmosphere as the following: "..., she saw Mr. Darcy walk into the room. In an hastened manner he immediately began an enquiry after her health, imputing his visit to a wish of hearing that she were better. She answered him with cold civility. He sat down for a few moments, and then getting up, walked about the room. Elizabeth was amazed, but said not a word."¹⁰² Though Elizabeth loved Mr. Darcy she ignored him because as an individual woman she did not mean to be suppressed by a man. The main reason of Elizabeth's being angry and silent is that she could not tolerate discrimination toward her family when Darcy's friend's family presented.

"In vain have I wrestled. It will not do. My emotions will not be repressed. You must allow me to tell you how ardently I am fond of and love you."¹⁰³ Mr. Darcy who initially did not accept Elizabeth's having independent manner confessed her then.

After refusal she, at last, confesses her love in her talk with her father:

"I do, I do like him," she answered, with tears in her eyes, "I love him. No doubt that he has no improper pride. He is perfectly warm. You do not know what he really is; then pray do not torture me by speaking of him in such terms."¹⁰⁴

Pride and Prejudice is widely regarded as a masterpiece of world literature. It is one of the cherished books in English literature ranking as the most loved and one of the most favored novels of all times. It has been adapted into numerous stage productions and even more films. Despite the fact the plot of the novel is realistic it is full of romantic features which draws readers' attention deeply involving into the imagination of Jane Austin.

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¹⁰² Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

¹⁰³ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.

¹⁰⁴ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. New York: Penguin Classics, 2003.